

Influence of Social Media Use on Body Image and Self-Esteem among Senior High Students in Davao City

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Suggested Citation

Carballo, R.C., Helardez, J.M., Nasara, R.S., Canchico, F.D., & Bangeles, D.M.M. (2024). Influence of Social Media Use on Body Image and Self-Esteem among Senior High Students in Davao City. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 371-384.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).31](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).31)

Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the influence of social media on the body image and self-esteem among senior high school students in Davao City. Utilizing a quantitative research design, the study collected data from 100 senior high school students through structured questionnaires. Established measures were used to assess social media usage, perceived body image, and self-esteem, with strict adherence to ethical considerations and data confidentiality. The findings indicate high self-esteem across personal, social, and appearance-related domains. Additionally, social media use is high, highlighting its significant role in fulfilling academic, social, entertainment, and informational needs. Moreover, findings indicate

a moderate perception of body image that while students feel positively about certain aspects of their bodies, such as satisfaction and appearance maintenance behaviors, they also face challenges or pressures in areas like response to criticism and body modification preferences. Significant links were found with Academic, Socialization, and Informativeness aspects, but not with Entertainment. Overall social media usage correlated with perceived body image. Moreover, Socialization and Informativeness significantly predicted both body image and self-esteem among students. These findings underscore the influence of positive social interactions and informative content on social media in shaping adolescents' perceptions of themselves. This study contributes to the broader understanding of addressing social media's impact in schools. It highlights the roles of administrators, teachers, and students in promoting media literacy, resilience, and positive mental health outcomes. Future research can build upon these findings to develop effective intervention strategies.

Keywords: *Social Media Use, Body Image, Self-Esteem, Social Comparison Theory, Gratifications Theory.*

Introduction

The influence of social media use on body image and self-esteem among senior high students in Davao City is undoubtedly detrimental. With the incessant bombardment of unrealistic beauty standards and flawless portrayals on platforms like Instagram and TikTok, young individuals are constantly comparing themselves to unattainable ideals. Self-esteem plays a pivotal role in various domains of life. High self-esteem is associated with resilience, optimism, and better stress management. Individuals with high self-esteem are more likely to pursue their goals, cope with setbacks, and maintain healthy interpersonal relationships. Conversely, low self-esteem is linked to mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and eating disorders. It can hinder academic and professional achievement, as well as contribute to social withdrawal and relationship problems. Body image is a multifaceted construct that encompasses an individual's perceptions, thoughts, and feelings about their own body. It is influenced by a complex interplay of biological, psychological, and social factors, and has significant implications for mental and physical health. In contemporary society, where media portrayals of idealized body types are ubiquitous, understanding body image has become increasingly important.

Research consistently shows that social media use has a negative impact on body image and self-esteem, particularly among young women. Puglia (2017) found that body comparison tendency and motivation for social media use were negatively correlated with body esteem, with Facebook use having the largest negative impact. Silva and Penaforte (2020) further supported these findings, noting that social networks increase body dissatisfaction and influence the body type users aspire to have. Yang et al. (2020) provided a cognitive-affective model, showing that excessive social media use can lead to unhealthy body esteem through intensified cognitive internalization, appearance comparisons, and social appearance anxiety.

To investigate the specific types of social media content (e.g., images, videos, posts) that have the most significant impact on body image and self-esteem among senior high students in Davao City. This could include examining the prevalence of certain types of content, such as images depicting idealized body types or posts promoting specific beauty standards, and how exposure to these types of content influences students' perceptions of their own bodies and levels of self-esteem. Conducting this study is essential for gaining a deeper understanding of how social media impacts the mental health of senior high students in Davao City and can inform strategies to support their well-being in the digital age.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of social media use among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City in terms of:
 - 1.1. academic;
 - 1.2. socialization;
 - 1.3. entertainment; and
 - 1.4. informativeness?
2. What is the level of perceived body image of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City in terms of:
 - 2.1. body image satisfaction;
 - 2.2. appearance maintenance behaviors;
 - 2.3. response to external criticism and social pressure; and
 - 2.4. body modification preferences and attitudes?
3. What is the level of self-esteem of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City in terms of:
 - 3.1. performance self-esteem;
 - 3.2. social self-esteem; and
 - 3.3. appearance self-esteem?

4. Is there a combined significant relationship between social media use and the outcome variables body image and self-esteem among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City?

5. Does social media use significantly influence the outcome variables body image and self-esteem among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no combined significant relationship between social media use and the outcome variables body image and self-esteem among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City?

H₀₂: Social media use does not significantly influence the outcome variables body image and self-esteem among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City?

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in **Social Comparison Theory**. Social comparison theory suggests that people value their own personal and social worth by assessing how they compare to others. Introduced by Leon Festinger in 1954, the theory describes the comparison processes people utilize to evaluate their actions, accomplishments, and opinions in contrast to those of other people. This will support our study by explaining how people compare themselves to others on social media. This comparison will lead to dissatisfaction with their bodies and lower self-esteem due to exposure to idealized images, selective self-presentation, reinforcement of beauty norms, and seeking validation through likes and comments. Our study aims to explore how these dynamics affect individuals' body image and self-esteem in the context of social media use. Kasirye (2021) coined in the early 1940s by Katz and Blumler (1974), the uses and **Gratifications theory** deals with understanding why people use certain types of media, what needs do they have to use them, and what gratifications do they get from using them. For example, they might use social media to seek validation or social support, compare themselves to others, or enhance their self-image

by curating their online presence. Understanding these motivations can help explain how social media use influences body image and self-esteem.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Method

This quantitative research utilized the descriptive-correlational method. This research design deemed appropriate for this study since it aimed to determine the possible existence of relationships among the variable's understudies. Descriptive research is defined as a research method that involves observing behavior to describe attributes objectively and systematically. A descriptive research project seeks to comprehend phenomena or groups in depth. Correlational research, on the other hand, is a method that describes and predicts how variables are naturally related in the real world without the researcher attempting to alter them or assign causation between them.

Descriptive correlational research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. The researchers collected data to explain the variables of interest and figure out how they relate.

Participants and Sampling

This study involved 100 SHS students of legal age (18 and up) in Davao City. The participants were selected based on specific inclusion criteria, and purposive sampling was used. It was made clear to the participants that their participation was voluntary, and their withdrawal would be respected.

Data Collection

The researchers followed several steps to gather data for this study. These steps included validating the survey questionnaire guide with experts, revising the manuscript based on the professors' recommendations, obtaining approval from the Ethics Review Committee, and conducting the survey questionnaire online using Google Forms. The researchers made sure that the safety of the participants was upheld throughout the process.

Data Analysis

The subsequent steps in analyzing the obtained data were done by the researchers: Upon getting the necessary information via the data-gathering procedure outlined in this manuscript, the researchers then encoded the gathered data to make a table, which was the basis for computation. Data analysis was conducted by the researchers. After the desired themes were generated from the data analysis, crafting of the remaining parts of the paper followed.

Ethical Consideration

This study was conducted per ethical guidelines set forth by the DOST Philippine Health Research Board and the Code of Conduct by the American Psychological Association (2017). The researchers obtained informed consent from participants, ensuring their rights were respected, and allowed participants to withdraw from the study at any time. Pseudonyms were used to maintain confidentiality. The researchers avoided plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, and adhered to ethical protocols set forth by APA.

Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the level of social media use among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. The instrument has 19 items with four indicators namely: Academic, Socialization, Entertainment, and informativeness.

Table 1. Summary of the Level of Social Media Use among Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

Indicator	Mean	Description
Academic	3.83	High
Socialization	3.61	High
Entertainment	4.00	High
Informativeness	3.79	High
Overall	3.81	High

As shown in the Table 1 above, academic, socialization, entertainment, and informativeness all yielded a high level with a mean of 3.83, 3.61, 4.00, and 3.79, respectively. The high score in this category indicates that social media is predominantly used for entertainment purposes among senior high school students. They likely spend in social media sites sharing pictures, look at funny sharing, watching movies and sites to get relief from academic stress. Overall, the level of social media use is high among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. This suggests that social media plays a significant role in their daily lives, fulfilling various needs related to academic, social, entertainment, and informational purposes.

Wang and Xie (2023) highlight the role of social media in socializing, learning, and entertainment, with Instagram being a dominant platform. This is also supported by Alghamdi, G. M. A. (2022) that Instagram (IG) is among the most popular social media platforms, and is used by millions of people every day, especially young adults. Dhanwal et al. (2022) emphasizes the impact of social media on teaching and learning activities, and the use of various platforms for information sharing and entertainment. According to the study of Alenezi and Brinthaupt (2022), students frequently used social media for casual

networking and amusing, but not as frequently as a formal teaching aid. The majority of pupils thought that social media promoted interaction, participation from peers and teachers, group learning, and engagement. With this it will also improve their independence in working and finding educational resources according to Ibraev, A. D. (2024).

Table 2 shows the level of perceived body image of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. The instrument has 35 items with four indicators namely: Body image satisfaction, Appearance maintenance behaviors, Response to external criticism and social pressure, and Body modification preferences and attitudes.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Perceived Body Image of Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

Indicator	Mean	Description
1	3.69	High
2	3.59	High
3	2.73	Moderate
4	2.62	Moderate
Overall	3.16	Moderate

Note: 1 - Body image satisfaction; 2 - Appearance maintenance behaviors; 3 - Response to external criticism and social pressure; 4 - Body modification preferences and attitudes.

As shown in Table 2, the level of perceived body image of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. Body Image satisfaction and appearance maintenance behaviors show high levels with a mean of 3.69 and 3.59 respectively. This suggests that students tend to feel positive about their bodies and have high engagement in behaviors aimed at maintaining appearance. Response to external criticism and social pressure; and body modification preferences and attitudes both show moderate level with a mean of 2.73 and 2.62 respectively. These findings collectively reflect a balanced perspective, wherein students are moderately responsive to external pressures related to body image and also exhibit a moderate level of

interest in body modification practices. Overall the mean score is 3.16, indicating a moderate perception of body image among the senior high school students in the selected schools. This suggests that while there are areas where students feel positively about their bodies (such as satisfaction and appearance maintenance behaviors), there are also areas where they may face challenges or pressures (such as response to criticism and body modification preferences).

Sundgot-Borgen et al. (2021) found that while female exercise science students had higher body appreciation, both male and female students experienced body appearance pressure, particularly in fitness centers. Poulter and Trehame (2021), and Piko and Mellor (2020) shed light on the factors contributing to positive body image, such as critical media engagement, functional conceptualization of the body, and self-esteem. Jarman et al. (2021) which hypothesized that higher intensity of social media and appearance-focused use would relate to lower body satisfaction and lower well-being directly and indirectly through higher thin- and muscular-ideal internalization and social and appearance comparisons, was partially supported. Michael and Agus (2020) found a significant association between body image and self-esteem among female students, indicating a potential impact on mental health. Arora and Joseph (2017) similarly highlighted the importance of body image perception, particularly in relation to BMI. Toselli et al. (2023) further emphasized the role of gender, weight status, and physical activity in shaping body image perception. Evangelista et al. (2016) identified a prevalence of body image dissatisfaction, particularly among girls, those with higher weight, and those experiencing negative emotions.

Table 3 shows the level of self-esteem of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. The instrument has 20 items with three indicators namely: Personal self-esteem, Social self-esteem, and Appearance self-esteem.

Table 3. Summary of the Level of Self-Esteem of Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

Indicator	Mean	Description
Personal self-esteem	3.45	High
Social self-esteem	3.63	High
Appearance self-esteem	3.46	High
Overall	3.51	High

Table 3 shows the level of self-esteem of senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City. Personal self-esteem, social self-esteem, and appearance self-esteem all yielded to high level with a mean of 3.45, 3.63, and 3.46, respectively. The overall mean score of 3.51 reflects a high level of self-esteem across all measured indicators. This indicates that senior high school students in the selected schools in Davao City generally possess a positive and confident sense of self in various aspects of their lives, including personal, social, and appearance-related domains.

The influence of age and social context on self-esteem has also been explored, with first year college students found to have higher self-esteem than their senior high school counterparts (Fabella, 2019). This aligns with earlier research indicating that self-esteem generally increases with age during adolescence and early adulthood as individuals gain more social experience and autonomy (Robins & Trzesniewski, 2005; Orth & Luciano, 2018). Moreover, the transition to college often provides new opportunities for self-discovery and achievement, which can enhance self-esteem (Chung et al., 2014). The study of Rosemond & Owens (2018), supports that the college environment itself plays a crucial role in fostering personal growth. The transition to this new setting encourages students to engage in self-exploration and identity development, enhancing their overall self-esteem.

Predictors	Pearson Correlation	Strength of the Relationship	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Academic	.214*	Weak	.033	Significant	Reject H ₀
Socialization	.423**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Entertainment	.174	Weak	.084	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Informativeness	.439**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
SM Use	.385**	Weak	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Outcome: perceived body image
**** Correlation is Significant at 0.01 Level (2-tailed)**
N = 100

Figure 2. Test of Relationship between Social Media Use and Perceived Body Image among Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

Pearson product-moment correlation was computed to assess the relationship between social media use and perceived body image among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City.

It was found that there is a significant relationship between social media use and its other indicators, and perceived body image except for one. (Academic [$r = .214^*$, $n = 100$, $p = .033 < 0.05$], Socialization [$r = .423^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$], Informativeness [$r =$

$.439^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$], Entertainment [$r = .174$, $n = 100$, $p = .084 > 0.05$], and overall SM use [$r = .385^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$]).

The results suggest that socialization-related and informativeness-related social media use are moderately correlated with perceived body image among senior high school students, while academic-related and overall social media use have weaker correlations. Entertainment-related social media use, however, does not appear to be

significantly associated with perceived body image.

Media analysis has been shown to change attitudes towards body image (Rabak-Wagener et al., 1998), with a significant change in beliefs

observed in college students who analyzed and reframed fashion advertisements. Nezelek (1999) found that self-perceptions of body and social attractiveness were positively related to the intimacy experienced in social interactions.

Predictors	Pearson Correlation	Strength of the Relationship	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Academic	.351**	Weak	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Socialization	.483**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Entertainment	.362**	Weak	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Informativeness	.559**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
SM Use	.548**	Moderate	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Outcome: self-esteem
******. Correlation is Significant at 0.01 Level (2-tailed)
N = 100

Figure 3. Test of Relationship between Social Media Use and Self-Esteem among Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

Pearson product-moment correlation was computed to assess the relationship between social media use and self-esteem among senior high school students in selected schools in Davao City.

It was found that there is a significant relationship between social media use and all its indicators, and self-esteem. (Academic [$r = .351^*$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$], Socialization [$r = .483^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$], Entertainment [$r = .362^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$] and Informativeness [$r = .559^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$], and overall SM use [$r = .548^{**}$, $n = 100$, $p = .000 < 0.05$]).

The results suggest that social media use, whether it be academic-related, socialization-related, entertainment-related, or informative, is positively correlated with self-esteem among senior high school students. These findings indicate that different aspects of social media use can influence students' self-esteem, with socialization and informativeness showing particularly strong associations.

Köse and Dogan (2019) found a moderate negative correlation between social media addiction and self-esteem, with higher addiction levels among those with more Instagram followers. Similarly, Hawi and Samaha (2017) reported a negative association between addictive social media use and self-esteem, with self-esteem mediating the effect of addiction on life satisfaction. These findings are consistent with other research indicating that excessive social media use can negatively impact self-esteem by promoting unhealthy comparisons and reducing face-to-face interactions (Andreassen et al., 2017; Kross et al., 2013). This aligns with **Social Comparison Theory**, particularly in aspects like Socialization and Informativeness, and perceived body image suggest that students may engage in upward or downward social comparisons regarding their appearance, leading to changes in their body image perceptions.

Model Summary		R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE
1		.499	.249	.218	.36020
<i>Coefficients</i>					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	B	SE B	β		
(Constant)	1.913	.287		6.653	.000
Academic	-.064	.085	-.089	-.748	.456
Socialization	.242	.091	.319	2.666	.009
Entertainment	-.046	.065	-.079	-.709	.480
Informativeness	.210	.071	.336	2.950	.004

Figure 4. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Social Media Use to the Perceived Body Image of Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

As shown in the table above, the results of the regression indicated that the predictors explained 24.9% of the variance [$R^2 = .249$, $F(4,95) = 7.895$, $p = .000^b$]. It was found out that Socialization ($\beta = .242$, $p = .009 < .05$) significantly predicted perceived body image among the respondents. In the same manner, Informativeness ($\beta = .210$, $p = .004 < .05$) significantly predicted perceived body image among the respondents.

The regression analysis unveiled that socialization and informativeness significantly predict perceived body image among senior high school students, collectively explaining 24.9% of the variance. Socialization via social media and informativeness emerged as critical factors, with regression coefficients indicating that for every unit increase in socialization, there is an approximate .242-unit increase in perceived body image. For every unit increase in informativeness, there is an approximate .210-unit increase. These findings emphasize the critical role of social media interactions and information consumption in shaping adolescent body image perceptions. Such insights highlight the importance of considering both the quantity and quality of social media engagement when addressing body image concerns among youth.

The significant predictors of perceived body image and self-esteem, such as Socialization and Informativeness, highlight how students seek gratification from social media interactions and informative content, which in turn influence their perceptions of themselves and their overall self-esteem. Vicente-Benito and Ramirez-Duran (2023); Nierengarten (2017) further support these findings, with Vicente-Benito noting the negative impact of social media on body image and well-being, and Nierengarten emphasizing the potential for visually oriented platforms to have a detrimental effect. According to Tiggemann and Slater (2014), exposure to idealized images on social media can lead to body dissatisfaction, especially among young women. This dissatisfaction stems from the constant comparison to unrealistic body standards presented online. Several mechanisms explain how social media affects body image. Social comparison theory posits that individuals compare themselves to others who appear more attractive, leading to negative self-evaluations (Festinger, 1954). Furthermore, the portrayal of idealized bodies through filters and editing tools can exacerbate these comparisons, making the standards even more unattainable (Perloff, 2014).

Model Summary	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE
1	.597	.356	.329	.33681

<i>Coefficients</i>					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	B	SE B	β		
(Constant)	1.791	.269		6.662	.000
Academic	-.019	.080	-.027	-.242	.809
Socialization	.170	.085	.221	1.997	.049
Entertainment	.053	.060	.091	.882	.380
Informativeness	.256	.067	.405	3.843	.000

Figure 5. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Social Media Use to the Self-Esteem of Senior High School Students in Selected Schools in Davao City

As shown in the table above, the results of the regression indicated that the predictors explained 35.6% of the variance [$R^2 = .356$, $F(4,95) = 13.150$, $p = .000^b$]. It was found out that Socialization ($\beta = .170$, $p = .049 < .05$) significantly predicted self-esteem among the respondents. In the same manner, Informativeness ($\beta = .256$, $p = .000 < .05$) significantly predicted self-esteem among the senior high school students.

The predictors, collectively, accounted for a substantial portion of the variance in self-esteem, with an R-squared value of .356, indicating that 35.6% of the variation in self-esteem scores can be attributed to the variables under consideration and among these predictors, socialization, and informativeness emerged as significant contributors to self-esteem. The regression coefficients demonstrate that socialization through social media, represented by a β coefficient of .170, and informativeness, with a β coefficient of .256, have notable impacts on self-esteem. Specifically, for every unit increase in socialization, there is an approximate .170-unit increase in self-esteem, while a one-unit increase in informativeness corresponds to a substantial .256-unit increase in self-esteem among respondents. These findings highlight the influence of social media interactions and the quality of information consumed in shaping adolescents' self-esteem. It suggests that fostering positive social interactions and access to informative content may be instrumental in

promoting healthier self-esteem levels among high school students.

Ma (2022) found that the type of online activity, particularly social interaction, can influence self-esteem, with females reporting higher levels. However, Muigai (2020) and Stenly (2017) both found no significant relationship between social media interaction and self-esteem. Valkenburg et al. (2006) found that the type and quality of interactions on social media platforms significantly affect adolescents' self-esteem. Positive interactions and feedback can enhance self-esteem, while negative experiences can lead to its decline. Studies indicate that social media platforms can serve as important venues for social interaction, providing opportunities for users to receive social support and validation (Ellison et al., 2007). It has been shown that consuming informative and educational content can positively influence self-esteem by providing individuals with knowledge and a sense of competence (Park & Lee, 2014). Metzger et al. (2010), who argue that exposure to informative content on social media enhances self-efficacy and self-esteem. Additionally, media literacy programs can equip students with the skills to navigate social media effectively, discerning between valuable information and potentially harmful content (Livingstone, 2014).

Summary

The researchers wanted to determine the influence of social media use to the perceived body image and self-esteem of respondents of this study. The researchers included academic, socialization, entertainment, and informativeness as social media use indicators.

For the research design, the researchers utilized quantitative research by means of descriptive-correlational design. Further, the researchers utilized adapted and modified survey questionnaires as the tool used in gathering the necessary data. The respondents were senior high school students enrolled in the Academic Year 2023-2024 in Davao City. There was a total of 100 respondents for this study. To analyze the data, the researchers used descriptive statistics which includes the mean and standard deviation to determine the levels of social media use, perceived body image, and self-esteem and its indicators. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and multiple linear regression were used to determine the relationship and influence of the variables in this study.

With this, the results of the study are as follows:

The data illustrates the extent of social media use among senior high school students in Davao City, divided into categories such as Academic, Socialization, Entertainment, and Informativeness. All categories scored highly on average.

The perceived body image among senior high school students in Davao City encompasses aspects like Body Image Satisfaction, Appearance Maintenance Behaviors, Response to External Criticism and Social Pressure, and Body Modification Preferences and Attitudes. Body Image Satisfaction and Appearance Maintenance Behaviors both have high scores, whereas Response to External Criticism and Body Modification Preferences are at moderate levels. The overall mean score indicates a moderate perception of body image.

The self-esteem levels of senior high school students in Davao City were examined across Personal, Social, and Appearance self-esteem.

All indicators received high mean scores, resulting in an overall mean of high.

The relationship between social media use and perceived body image was analyzed using Pearson correlation. Significant correlations were found between perceived body image and the Academic, Socialization, and Informativeness aspects of social media use, whereas Entertainment showed no significant correlation. Overall social media use was significantly correlated with perceived body image.

The results of the regression indicated that Socialization and informativeness significantly predicted perceived body image among the respondents. Additionally, it was found out that Socialization and Informativeness also significantly predicted self-esteem among the senior high school students.

Conclusions

This study aimed to discover the influence of social media use on body image and self-esteem among senior high students in Davao City. The focus was to determine the level of social media use and its indicators, the level of perceived body image and its indicators, the level of self-esteem and its indicators, the relationship between social media use and the outcome variables body image and self-esteem, as well as determine if social media use significantly influence perceived body image and self-esteem among senior high students in Davao City.

The data illustrates the extent of social media use among senior high school students in Davao City, divided into categories such as Academic, Socialization, Entertainment, and Informativeness. All categories scored highly on average. This high level of social media engagement suggests that these platforms play a crucial role in various aspects of students' lives, fulfilling their academic, social, entertainment, and informational needs.

The perceived body image among senior high school students in Davao City encompasses aspects like Body Image Satisfaction, Appearance Maintenance Behaviors, Response

to External Criticism and Social Pressure, and Body Modification Preferences and Attitudes. Body Image Satisfaction and Appearance Maintenance Behaviors both have high scores, whereas Response to External Criticism and Body Modification Preferences are at moderate levels. The overall mean score indicates a moderate perception of body image, suggesting that while students generally feel positive about their bodies, they still face challenges related to external pressures and body modification desires.

The self-esteem levels of senior high school students in Davao City were examined across Personal, Social, and Appearance self-esteem. All indicators received high mean scores, resulting in an overall mean of high. This indicates that students possess a positive and confident sense of self across different domains, reflecting their overall well-being and self-assurance.

The relationship between social media use and perceived body image was analyzed using Pearson correlation. Significant correlations were found between perceived body image and the Academic, Socialization, and Informativeness aspects of social media use, whereas Entertainment showed no significant correlation. Overall social media use was significantly correlated with perceived body image. This suggests that social media use, particularly for socialization and informativeness, moderately influences body image perceptions among students.

The results of the regression indicated that Socialization and Informativeness significantly predicted perceived body image among the respondents. Additionally, it was found that Socialization and Informativeness also significantly predicted self-esteem among the senior high school students. These findings emphasize the importance of positive social interactions and informative content on social media in shaping both body image and self-esteem, highlighting the need for mindful engagement with these platforms to support adolescent development.

Recommendations

Administrators in school may develop educational programs to increase awareness about social media's impact. Foster a supportive school culture that values individual differences and offers counseling services.

Teachers can integrate media literacy into the curriculum and promote discussions on body positivity. Encourage critical thinking about media messages and celebrate diversity in the classroom.

Senior high school students can practice mindful social media use by limiting exposure to negative content and focusing on personal strengths. Engage in activities outside of social media to build self-esteem.

For future researchers to conduct longitudinal studies to explore long-term effects. Investigate intervention strategies to mitigate negative impacts and promote media literacy and resilience among adolescents.

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